

Effects of long day on panicle characteristics.^a Beijing, China.

Line	Spikelet number/panicle length		Seed-setting rate (%)	
	SD	LD	SD	LD
Nongken 58	2.83	2.23	84.1 ± 2.7	55.0 ± 11.0
Nongken 58s	3.92	3.21	77.1 ± 3.1	0
Nongken 58sr	4.55	2.94	84.9 ± 4.9	51.2 ± 5.0

^aPlants treated with 7 d SD to induce panicle initiation then exposed to either SD or LD. Data collected from main tillers: average of more than three plants.

panicle length (RSL), and seed-setting rate (SSR). The experiment was repeated three times.

The data from treatments 1-10 confirmed that the LD did postpone the transition from vegetative to reproductive growth of the late japonica lines tested. What was interesting to us was that the LD applied after panicles were initiated (a minimum of 5 d SD treatment) was able to significantly delay their development and resulted in delayed heading (see figure, a-c, treat-

ments 11-18). We found no obvious LD-delaying effect in the indica line W6154s (see figure, d, treatments 12, 14, 16, and 18). Furthermore, when scored by Ding's panicle development index, the slower panicle development under LD conditions was at least one of the major reasons, if not the only reason, for the delay of heading under treatments 11-18 (data not shown).

Not only did speed of panicle development as a whole slow down, but also organogenesis events were affected.

As shown in the table, the LD conditions decreased both RSL and SSR. The lower RSL and SSR under LD might have resulted from the unfavorable effect of LD on both spikelet primordia initiation and male organogenesis.

Our data suggested that LD affects not only the male fertility in Nongken 58s but also other aspects of panicle development. They provide a new basis for understanding of the mechanism of the photoperiod-sensitive male sterility in Nongken 58s—i.e., impairment results in a failure of male organogenesis to respond properly to normal LD leaf signals, a failure that affects nonspecifically various aspects of panicle development. Further research on the mechanism of conditional male sterility, therefore, should focus on the response of male organogenesis to environmental signals. ■

Rice varieties of Kerala as restorers and maintainers for wild abortive cytoplasmic male sterile lines

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Rice hybrids developed and released by research stations and private companies in India have limited adoption in Kerala because consumers there prefer bold, red kernel rice varieties. Hybrid rice programs were initiated recently to boost production in the state, where rice is the staple food for more than 90% of the population. As a first step, we identified restorers and maintainers for the exotic cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines collected from other rice centers.

Three exotic CMS lines of wild abortive (WA) origin—V20 A, IR58025 A, and IR62829 A—were crossed with 43 male parents from the source germplasm, including 26 locally released varieties and 17 elite varieties devel-

Table 1. Maintainers and restorers for WA CMS lines. Kerala, India. 1994-95.^a

Genotype	Kernel color	CMS lines			Genotype	Kernel color	CMS lines		
		V20 A	IR58025 A	IR62829 A			V20 A	IR58025 A	IR62829 A
PTB7	Red	PF	S	S	MO 8	Red	S	S	S
PTB10	Red	-	-	S	MO 9	Red	S	S	S
PTB32	Red	PF	PF	PF	MO 10	Red	-	PF	PF
PTB35	Red	S	S	S	MO 11	Red	PF	PF	PF
PTB36	White	S	S	S	PMK2	White	F	F	F
PTB37	White	S	S	S	ADT36	White	PF	PF	PF
PTB38	White	S	S	S	ADT37	White	F	F	F
PTB39	Red	S	S	S	ADT39	White	PF	-	-
PTB40	Red	S	S	S	ADT42	White	F	-	-
PTB41	Red	PF	PF	PF	ASD16	White	PF	PF	-
PTB42	White	S	S	S	TPS1	White	PF	-	PF
PTB43	White	-	F	F	C043	White	PF	-	-
PTB45	Red	PF	PF	PF	JJ92	White	S	S	S
PTB46	White	PF	PF	PF	Bas370	White	S	S	S
PTB47	White	F	F	F	IR20	White	PF	PF	PF
PTB49	Red	S	S	S	IR36	White	-	-	PF
PTB50	Red	PF	PF	PF	IR42	White	F	F	-
PTB51	Red	S	S	S	IR50	White	-	PF	-
PTB52	Red	S	S	S	IR64	White	PF	-	F
MO 4	Red	S	S	S	MDU4	White	F	-	-
MO 6	Red	PF	PF	PF	Madhurt	White	S	-	-
MO 7	Red	S	S	S					

^aS = sterile, F = fertile, PF = partially sterile.

oped outside the state, during the 1994 wet season to produce 107 F₁ hybrids. The hybrids and their parents were transplanted in the main field during the following dry season in rows of 10 plants spaced at 15 × 20cm. Five pani-

cles from each plant were used to study fertility behavior.

A few florets each from the upper, middle, and lower part of the panicles were collected before anthesis, and pollen fertility was identified with 2%,

Table 2. Frequency of restorers, partial restorers, and maintainers for V20 A in red- and white-kernel rice varieties. Kerala, India. 1994-95.

Varietal group	Lines (no.)	Restorers	Partial restorers	Maintainers
Red kernel	17	0 (0) ^a	7 (41.2)	10 (58.8)
White kernel	21	6 (28.6)	8 (38.0)	7 (33.4)

^aFigures in parentheses indicate percentages.

IKI stain. Three panicles each from the same plant were bagged before flowering to facilitate selfing. Spikelet fertility was calculated as percentage of filled grains. Hybrids showing >80% pollen and spikelet fertility were classified as fertile, those with 100% pollen and spikelet sterility were considered sterile, and the rest were classified as partially fertile. Accordingly, the male

parents were classified as restorers, maintainers, and partial restorers (Tables 1 and 2). Among the 43 varieties tested, 18 were effective maintainers, 7 effective restorers, and 16 partial restorers. The response of two varieties depended on the female parent used (maintainer/restorer for one CMS line and partial restorer for the other), indicating the influence of the genetic background of

the female parent on the nuclear gene expression of the male parent. The frequency of main-tainers and partial restorers was very high among the red-kernel rice varieties, but practically nil among complete restorers. Hybrids with the red-kernel Kerala rice varieties when used as male parents were either sterile or partially fertile, but none was completely fertile. The sterile hybrids are being back-crossed with some of the identified maintainers (PTB39, PTB52, MO 4, MO 8, etc.) to develop locally adaptable CMS lines with red kernels for future use in hybrid rice development. The fertile hybrids are being assessed for their heterosis and adaptability under different conditions. ■

Machhapuchhre 3 (MP3), the first rice variety developed through a participatory plant breeding approach released for mid to high altitudes of Nepal

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Adoption rates for exotic rice varieties in the eastern and western hills of Nepal are reported to be 10-11%. Seven F₅ bulks representing three crosses—Fuji 102/CD, K332/NR10157-2B-2, and Stejaree 45/CD—were given to expert farmers identified through a village workshop. They were asked to grow and manage the new entries along with their local variety in the same way. The participatory plant breeding (PPB) system included a farm walk to different trial sites, preference ranking, measurement of farmers' managed yield data, postharvest evaluations by women farmers, and monitoring of varietal spread. Farmer-selected lines were also included in national yield trials to satisfy variety release require-

Comparison of the means of top five conventionally bred varieties (CBVs) with that of Machhapuchhre 3.

ments. In contrast to conventional breeding practices, most farmers grew the new entries in medium fertility conditions. A few farmers chose plots they regarded as problematic. The overall strategy emphasized risk aversion and expanding successful lines to better fields. Decisions on retaining or rejecting any rice entry was largely taken after women farmers thoroughly evaluated postharvest traits, such as white grain color along with aroma, softness of cooked rice, and ability to expand and remain dry after cooking. Focused group discussion with the farmers revealed that grain yield alone did not influence farmers' decision of adopting and spreading MP3 although the variety yielded well

even in the formal varietal trials (see figure). Machhapuchhre 3 has been officially released for altitudes between 1400 and 2000 m of western Nepal, on 14 Jul 1996, or less than 8 yr from the initial crossing in autumn 1988. This is the first recorded example of a successful variety developed by decentralized selection of segregating material through PPB drawing active participation of expert farmers. Experience from this experiment suggests that the PPB approach is a cost-effective and suitable method for developing farmers' need-based crop varieties. ■

Breeding of Z-Biao S line, the indica photothermosensitive genic male sterile line with recessive purple leaf maker

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We developed two photothermosensitive genic male sterile lines (PTGMS) with recessive purple leaf marker, Zi-Biao S-1 and Zi-Biao S-2, to eliminate seed contamination that may result from incomplete male sterility of PTGMS lines in a two-line, hybrid rice seed production system.